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Spray Drying in the Pharmaceutical Industry – A Review

C.J.Aundhia^{1*}, J A.Raval², M.M.Patel³, N.V Shah¹, S.P.Chauhan¹, G.U.Sailor¹, A.R.Javia¹,
R.A.Mahashwari¹

¹Department of Pharmacy, Sumandeep Vidyapeeth, Piparia, Vadodara, Gujarat 391670, India.

²S.K. Patel College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Mehsana-Gozaria highway, Kherva, Mehsana, Gujarat 382711, India.

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ABSTRACT

Spray drying is a technique which has a wide range of applications in the pharmaceutical industry. The unique possibilities for particle engineering, potent drug handling and continuous production makes spray drying the preferred tool in formulation departments in more and more companies. The present review highlights the instrumentation, advantages and the various applications of spray drying.

³Kalol Institute of Pharmacy, B/h Old Janpath Hotel, National Highway, Kalol, Gujarat 382721, India.

Corresponding author

C.J.Aundhia

Department of Pharmacy, Sumandeep Vidyapeeth, Piparia, Vadodara - 391760, Gujarat, India.

E-mail ID: aundhia@gmail.com, Mobile: 09898693793

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Introduction

Atomization of a solution of one or more solids via a nozzle, spinning disk or other device followed by evaporation of the solvent from the droplets is termed as spray drying¹. It is a unique unit operation transforming liquid to powder in a simple and robust continuous process. The liquid may be a solution, an emulsion, slurry, a paste or even a melt². Thus spray drying is the process of contacting an atomized stream to be dried with a gas stream that is at a higher temperature than the liquid stream. The higher temperature of the gas stream causes evaporation of the liquid from the droplets, forming particles³.

Spray drying is one of the oldest forms of drying and one of the few technologies available for the conversion of a liquid, slurry, or low-viscosity paste to a dry solid in one unit operation⁴. This process came to the fore during the Second World War although it was known and used much before that. The need to reduce the transport weight of foods and other materials led to developments in the technology that greatly expanded the range of products that could be successfully⁵.

Chart 1 gives an outline view of the spray drying process.

CHART 1: Main stages of spray Drying process

STAGES OF SPRAY DRYING

As a technique, spray drying consists of three basic stages:^{6,7}

(a) *Atomization*: Atomization is the process by which a liquid is disintegrated into many fine droplets. The formation of a spray with high surface/mass ratio is highly critical for optimum liquid evaporation conditions and, consequently, the desired properties of the resulting product. A liquid feed stock is atomized into droplets by means of a nozzle or rotary atomizer. Nozzles use pressure or compressed gas to atomize the feed while rotary atomizers employ an atomizer wheel rotating at high speed.

(b) *Drying and particle formation*: Hot process gas (air or nitrogen) is brought into contact with the atomized feed using a gas disperser, and evaporation

begins. The balance between temperatures, flow rate and droplet size controls the drying process. As the liquid rapidly evaporates from the droplet, a particle forms and falls to the bottom of the chamber.

(c) *Recovery*: The powder is recovered from the exhaust gases using a cyclone or a bag filter.

The whole process generally takes no more than a few seconds. Further, the liquid is dried, collected and delivered for further treatment without any intermediate manual handling. The spray drying process is applicable to a wide range of products and industries and plant capacities from a few g/h to 80 tons/h are available.

Figure 1 illustrates the main components of a spray dryer.⁷

FIGURE 1: Main components of a Spray dryer

ADVANTAGES OF SPRAY DRYING⁹

- Able to operate in applications that range from aseptic pharmaceutical processing to ceramic powder production.
- Can be designed to virtually any capacity required. Feed rates range from a few pounds per hour to over 100 tons per hour.
- Powder quality remains constant during the entire run of the dryer.
- Operation is continuous and adaptable to full automatic control.
- A great variety of spray dryer designs are available to meet various product specifications.
- Can be used with both heat-resistant and heat sensitive products.
- As long as they can be pumped, the feedstock can be abrasive, corrosive, flammable, explosive or toxic.
- Feedstock can be in solution, slurry, paste, gel, suspension or melt form.
- Product density can be controlled.
- Nearly spherical particles can be produced.
- Material does not contact metal surfaces until dried, reducing corrosion problems.

DISADVANTAGES OF SPRAY DRYING⁸

- It is not typically well suited for producing granules with mean particle size >200 μm
- It also has poor thermal efficiency at lower inlet temperatures and the exhaust air stream contains heat, which often requires sophisticated heat exchange equipment for removal.

INSTRUMENTATION

Every spray dryer consists of feed pump, atomizer, air heater, air disperser, drying chamber, and systems for exhaust air cleaning and powder recovery. Widely varying drying characteristics and quality requirements of the thousands of products spray dried determine the selection of the atomizer, the most suitable airflow pattern, and the drying chamber design. However in the design of the spray dryer, the residence time of individual particles inside the spray dryer is important. A particle should remain in the spray dryer long enough for complete evaporation of the solvent but not too long to cause product degradation, e.g., by charring³.

The main parts of a spray dryer are explained below:

Atomizer⁷:

Atomization is the process by which a liquid is disintegrated into many fine droplets. The atomizing

device, which forms the spray, is the ‘heart’ of the spray drying process. Following are the ideal requirements of an atomizer used in the spray drying process:

1. It must disperse the feed material into small droplets, which should be well distributed within the dryer and mixed thoroughly with the hot gas.
2. The size of the droplets produced must be compatible with the required product particle size characteristics.
3. The droplets produced must not be so large that they are incompletely dried, nor so small that product recovery is difficult. Small particles may also overheat and become scorched.
4. The atomizer must also act as a metering device, controlling the rate at which the material is fed into the dryer.

Table 1 lists the various types of atomizers used in the pharmaceutical industry and the mode of atomization of each:

TABLE 1

Types of atomizers and their mode of atomization

Sr. no	Atomizer type	Mode of atomization
1	Rotary Atomizer	Centrifugal Energy
2	Pressure Nozzle	Pressure Energy
3	Two fluid nozzle	Kinetic energy

a) Rotary atomizer

In Rotary atomizers the liquid is continuously accelerated to the wheel edge by centrifugal forces, produced by the rotation of the wheel^[14]. The liquid is distributed centrally and then extends over the wheel surface in a thin sheet, discharged at high speed at the periphery of the wheel. The degree of atomization from a rotating disc atomizer depends on the disk peripheral speed, feed rate, feed physical properties, and atomizer design. This degree of atomization in turn affects various properties of the finished product.

Such an investigation was carried out in which the effect of Rotary Disk Atomizer RPM on Particle Size Distribution in a Semi-Industrial Spray Dryer was studied¹⁰. It was found that maximum particle size was achieved when the atomizer speed reduced.

Rotary atomizers normally operate in the range of 5000–25,000 rpm with wheel diameter of 5–50 cm. The mean size of the droplet produced is inversely proportional to the wheel speed and directly proportional to the feed rate and its viscosity. Solid content and surface tension are the other factors having minor effects on the droplet size⁸.

The wheel should be designed, so that it will bring the liquid up to the peripheral speed prior to the disengagement. Very often the wheels are therefore with vanes of different design to prevent liquid slippage over the internal surface in the wheel. The vanes also concentrate the liquid at the disc edge, producing there a liquid film analogous to the one considered in pressure nozzles. The wheel will act as a fan and air is sucked into the concentrate due to the rotation. Different wheel designs and properties decide how much air is incorporated in the atomized droplets. Vane less (disk) designs are often applied when coarse powders are required at high production rates⁸.

b) Pressure nozzle¹¹

The basic function of pressure nozzles is to convert the pressure energy supplied by the high pressure pump into kinetic energy in form of a thin film, the stability of which is determined by the properties of the liquid such as viscosity, surface tension, density and quantity per unit of time, and by the medium into which the liquid is sprayed.

Most commercially available pressure nozzles are designed with a swirl chamber giving the liquid a rotation, so that it will leave the orifice, the second main component of a pressure nozzle, as a hollow cone.

Pressure nozzles are generally used to form coarse spray-dried particles (120– 300 mm mean particle size) with good flow properties. Antibiotics are a typical application for such a dryer⁷.

Figure 2 shows the mechanism of atomization of a rotary atomizer and pressure nozzle.

FIGURE 2

Figures illustrating the mechanism of action of (A) Rotary atomizer (B) Pressure nozzle

c) Two Fluid Nozzles

The available energy for atomization in two fluid atomizers is independent of liquid flow and pressure. The necessary (kinetic) energy for atomization is supplied by compressed air. The atomization is

created due to high frictional shearing forces between the liquid surface and the air having a high velocity even at sonic velocities and sometimes rotated to obtain maximum atomization. The mechanism of atomization is illustrated in figure 3.

FIGURE 3

Figures illustrating the mechanism of atomization of a two way nozzle

Two fluid atomization techniques is the only successful nozzle method of producing very small particles, especially from highly viscous liquids. This is the most common atomization technique used in the pharmaceutical industry.

A new type of atomizer which has been developed of late is the pulse combustion atomizer. Such a type of atomizer makes use of unstable hot air flow generated by a pulse combustor to atomize and dry liquid material¹².

Studies of influence of Atomizing Parameters on Droplet Properties in a Pulse Combustion Spray Dryer

were carried out during which it was concluded that all the three parameters investigated viz- Air flow oscillation frequency, velocity & density, and liquid material properties atomizing process is closely related with the atomizing process¹³.

Airflow in a Spray Dryer^{7, 11}:

Once the liquid is atomized it has to come into contact with drying air for evaporation to take place. This is done in a drying chamber. There are various modes of contact which influence the evaporation rates and product temperatures in the dryer. Following are the various configurations of the modes of contact (illustrated in figure 4):

FIGURE 4

Types of Airflow in a Spray dryer (A) Co- Current flow (B) Counter Current flow (C) Mixed flow

CHART 2: Classification of Spray Dryers

a) Co- current

Drying air and particles move through the drying chamber in the same direction. Product temperatures on discharge from the dryer are lower than the exhaust air temperature, and hence this is an ideal mode for drying heat sensitive products. The co current mode type of airflow is achieved using a rotary atomizer. The particle size of the powder produced is controlled through change of wheel speed¹⁴.

b) Counter- current

Drying air and particles move through the drying chamber in opposite directions. This mode is suitable for products, which require a degree of heat treatment during drying.

The temperature of the powder leaving the dryer is usually higher than the exhaust air temperatures. Such airflow is obtained by using a two fluid nozzle. The particle size is controlled by varying the nozzle flow ratio between compressed air and feed³¹.

c) Mixed flow

Particle movement through the drying chamber experiences both co- current and counter- current phases. This mode is suitable for heat stable products where coarse powder requirements necessitate the use of nozzle atomizers, spraying upwards into an incoming airflow or for heat sensitive products where

the atomizer sprays droplets downwards towards an integrated fluid bed and the air inlet and outlet are located at the top of the drying chamber.

Drying Chambers:

Various designs of drying chambers are seen on the market. The most common one is the cylindrical chamber with a cone of 40-60°, where gravity forces the powder to leave chamber. The drying chambers with a flat bottom require a scraper or suction device to remove the powder fraction from the chamber. Also horizontal box type drying chambers are seen, and they, too, operate with a forced powder removal system (i.e. scraper or screw)⁷.

Product Recovery:

Powder separation from the drying air follows the drying stage. In almost every case, spray-drying chambers have cone bottoms to facilitate the collection of the dried powder.

Two systems are utilized to collect the dried product. In the first type of system, when coarse powders are to be collected, they are usually discharged directly from the bottom of the cone through a suitable airlock, such as a rotary valve. The gas stream, now cool and containing all of the evaporated moisture, is drawn from the center of the cone above the cone bottom and discharged through a side outlet. The fines must be separated in a high-efficiency cyclone followed by a

wet scrubber or in a fabric filter (bag collector). Fines collected in the dry state are often added to the larger powder stream or recycled.

In the second type of system, total recovery of dried products takes place in the separation equipment. This type of system does not need a product-conveying system; therefore, the separation efficiency of the equipment becomes very critical.

Separation of dried product from the air influences powder properties by virtue of the mechanical

Classification based on the type of cycle:

a) Open cycle dryer

In an open cycle dryer, drying air is drawn from the atmosphere, heated, conveyed through the chamber and then exhausted to the atmosphere. This is by far the most commonly used design.

b) Closed Cycle dryer

A closed cycle dryer recycles the drying gas, which may be air or more commonly, an inert gas such as nitrogen. Closed cycle units are the dryers of choice when:

- Feedstock consists of solids mixed with flammable organic solvents when the product must not contact oxygen during drying.
- Complete recovery of solvent is required.
- The products are toxic.
- Pollution due to vapor, particulate emissions or odor is not permitted.
- Explosion risks must be eliminated.
- The powder will degrade by oxidation during drying.

c) Semi Closed spray dryer

This design is a cross between open and closed cycle dryers and it is not gas tight. There are many variations on this design, with the most important being the “direct heated” or “self-inertizing” system. In the self-inertizing design, a direct-fired heater is used and the air entering the system is limited to that required for combustion. An amount of air equal to

handling involved during the separation stage. Excessive mechanical handling can produce powders with a high percentage of fines.

CLASSIFICATION OF SPRAY DRYERS^{7,9}

Spray dryers can be classified into various types based on the type of cycle, type of stage and based on position. Chart 2 gives an overall view on the classification of the spray dryers.

the combustion air is bled from the system at the other end of the process. The gas (mainly products of combustion) is recycled through the dryer. The recycled gas has very low oxygen content, making it suitable for materials that cannot be exposed to oxygen, due to explosive hazard or product degradation.

Classification based on the type of stage:

a) Single stage spray dryer.

In a single stage dryer, the moisture is reduced to the target (typically 2% - 5% by weight) in one pass through the dryer. The single stage dryer is used in the majority of designs.

b) Two stage dryer

In a two stage dryer, the moisture content of product leaving the chamber is higher (typically 5% - 10%) than for the final product. After leaving the chamber, the moisture content is further reduced during a second stage. Second stage drying may be done in a fluidized bed dryer or a vibrating bed dryer. This two-stage drying concept achieves better overall heat economy and is suitable for many products which are heat sensitive.. When non-agglomerated powders of non-fat products are dried, a pneumatic transport system can replace the fluid bed. The various specialized two stage systems used in the pharmaceutical industry are described below:

➤ The Fluidized Spray Dryer

This combines spray drying and fluid bed drying technologies and offer excellent product flexibility

and excellent thermal efficiency. Pressure nozzles or a rotary atomizer spray the feed down towards the fluid bed where agglomeration incorporating finer, recycled material takes place. Exhaust air outlet is let through the roof causing further agglomeration in the spray zone. Sticky products can be dried successfully, and the concept is ideal for drying heat sensitive products, and improved aroma retention is accomplished. Agglomerated (instant), free-flowing dustless powders are obtained in systems based upon the integrated fluid bed or belt and a multi-stage concept where moist powder, produced during the first drying stage, forms agglomerates, which are after-dried and cooled in the following stages.

➤ Multi-Stage Dryer

The spray is created by a spray nozzle atomizer. Operational flexibility enables production of a wide range of physical properties. The process produces non-dusty, free flowing agglomerated powders with high flavor retention. It operates with low outlet temperatures, achieving high thermal efficiency. Dry ingredients for additional flavor or nutrient fortification can be added within the system to further promote capabilities and improve formulation efficiencies. This design concept is successful for drying high fats, hygroscopic, and sticky products that are difficult to handle in more conventional designs.

➤ Integrated Filter Dryer

This combines an integrated fluid bed and filter arrangement. It is an adaptable and flexible spray dryer for the food ingredients, food, dairy, chemical, and pharmaceutical industries.

The Integrated Filter Dryer features and benefits:

- ✓ Improves powder quality
- ✓ Total in-place recovery of powder
- ✓ Features integrated fluid bed
- ✓ Simplifies CIP operations
- ✓ No handling of product outside drying chamber
- ✓ Compact plant layout
- ✓ Reduced noise level

- ✓ Lower energy consumption

Classification based on the position of the spray dryer:

a) Horizontal

The chamber of a horizontal dryer has the form of a rectangular box with either a flat or a “V” shaped bottom. Nozzles in a box dryer normally spray horizontally, with the dried particles falling to the floor, where they are removed to a bagging area by a sweep conveyor or screw conveyor. Box dryers are usually small and the particle residence time relatively short, requiring the use of low flow nozzles, which produce relatively small particles.

b) Vertical

The chamber of a vertical (tower) dryer has the form of a tall cylinder with a cone-shaped bottom. Spray nozzles may be located at the top (co-current flow) or bottom (counter-current or mixed flow) of the chamber. Inlets for the drying air may be located at the top, bottom or side of the chamber. Vertical spray dryers are usually large and the residence time of sprayed particles is relatively long, allowing the use of higher flow nozzles such as the Tall form Dryer, which produce relatively large particles.

APPLICATIONS IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY¹⁵

Application in Primary Pharmaceuticals and excipients:

Active pharmaceutical ingredients are typically produced by extraction or chemical synthesis. In most cases the material is subsequently crystallized, mechanically separated. These steps are often replaced by spray drying. which not only helps control the residual moisture content in the powder but also to create materials with a tailor made particle size distribution, morphology and nature¹⁶.

Excipients like lactose can also be dried via spray drying process to obtain spray dried lactose. This is

directly compressible and also has better flowability. Other such example is tricalcium phosphate¹⁷.

Bioavailability^{6,18}:

Since many modern therapeutic compounds are most stable in a crystalline form, they often display poor aqueous solubility and low dissolution rates. This reduces the bioavailability of the API and slows absorption, sometimes to the point of failing to cause a therapeutic effect. With spray drying you can co-precipitate an API with a polymer in a stable amorphous solid dispersion, thereby greatly improving the dissolution rate.

Specifically, it is the unparalleled drying speed that allows the API to be captured in an amorphous form. By enhancing the dissolution rate in this way, spray drying has the potential to open the door for new, important treatments that are currently shelved due to low bioavailability.

Encapsulation¹⁸:

To achieve the efficient encapsulation, the drug is dissolved or suspended in a suitable (either aqueous or non-aqueous) solvent containing polymer materials. The solution or suspension is atomized into a drying chamber, and microparticles are formed by subsequent evaporation of the liquid^{19, 20, 21}. Encapsulation offers drug developers a number of commercial and medical advantages. It can be used for the sustained release of some antibiotics, reducing dosage requirements. By preventing drug concentration peaks, encapsulation is also an effective way to treat chronic illnesses, e.g., cancer or AIDS, and reduce side effects. On a more practical level, the technique is employed for taste masking and the physical protection of the API. Spray drying as well as spray congealing makes it possible to create particles in order to fashion specific controlled release patterns and other properties⁷.

The bioavailability of ibuprofen was increased by the encapsulation of ethanol and ibuprofen in a microcapsule by was spray drying technique. The

results showed an enhanced oral bioavailability of ibuprofen in the gelatin microcapsule and an increase in the absorption rate of ibuprofen due to the crystallinity change to amorphous form and increase in dissolution rate of ibuprofen in the gelatin microcapsule in rats. Thus, the ibuprofen-loaded gelatin microcapsule developed using spray-drying technique with gelatin would be useful to deliver ibuprofen in a pattern that allows fast absorption in the initial phase, leading to better absorption²².

Aseptic Production⁶:

Spray drying offers a number of advantages over traditional methods of aseptic drying such as freeze drying. More specifically, by allowing precise control of the drying process, spray drying affords far greater command over the shape, density and morphology of the final product. With lower running and capital costs, these advantages can be attained while reducing overheads.

Producing stabilized vaccines using spray drying reduces the need for refrigeration and makes their transport and storage far easier⁷

Inhalation^{6,18}:

Inhalation is a pain-free and self-administrable delivery method and for these reasons is preferred by patients and medical professionals, whenever applicable. Yet remarkably few inhaled treatments exist. The main reason for this is that although producing powders for inhalation is relatively easy on a small scale, it has been hard to replicate at a commercial level. The delivery of therapeutic macromolecules by inhalation, however, presents additional problems and challenges to produce fine powders of particle size 0.5 mm–5 mm that flow well during manufacture, filling, and emptying from the inhaler device,²³ but now highly specialized spray drying nozzles have been developed that help to achieve far greater particle engineering capabilities,

even at a large scale, making it possible to accurately manipulate aerodynamic particle size and flow properties. Consequently this technology makes it easier than ever before to efficiently produce therapies in the form of free-flowing particles of a small aerodynamic size, suitable for inhalation.

Powders can be designed for the rapid uptake or sustained release of medication. As a delivery method, inhalation is particularly relevant for commercializing biological compounds, e.g., hormones, peptides and proteins that risk degradation if ingested.

Using high-pressure homogenization and spray-drying techniques were used to develop a novel formulation of the drug Tobramycin for inhalation, composed of a mixture of micro- and nanoarticles in order to enhance lung deposition. The results from the spray-dried powders showed that the presence of nanoparticles in the formulations improved particle dispersion properties during inhalation²⁴

Compressibility, Flowability and Size Reduction:

Solid dosage pharmaceuticals often require a separate granulation step in the production cycle to avoid segregation and to produce a powder that has the correct flow properties to accommodate a high-speed tablet press. However, in the case of spray drying, granulation can be made an integral part of the continuous process. This not only results in a more streamlined, efficient production process, but reduces costs too.

In order to overcome the poor flowability and low compressibility of NaHCO₃, a spray-drying technique was used. Additives such as polyvinylpyrrolidone and silicon oil were found to be essential to obtain direct compressible spray-dried NaHCO₃. The product showed good compression characteristics without being transformed into sodium carbonate²⁵

Particles of microcrystalline size can also be obtained by spray-drying procedures, resulting in a porous, free-flowing, easily wetted, essentially monodispersed powder. With proper control of process variables,

spherical particles are obtained that may be coated with agents to aid suspension and promote stability. However, the process is not normally considered for the preparation of ultrafine powders.

Spray chilling²⁶:

Also called spray congealing or spray cooling it is a similar method to spray drying, but with different 'thermodynamic sign'. The same basic equipment as spray chilling is used as with spray drying although no heat is required. In this process, a drug substance is allowed to melt, disperse, or dissolve in hot melts of waxes, fatty acids, etc., and sprayed into an air chamber, where the temperature is below the melting temperatures of the formulation components, to provide spherical congealed pellets under appropriate processing conditions²⁷. In most cases, a product melt has a solidification curve. The melt is cooled to the solidification temperature; the solidification takes place at constant temperature by releasing the heat of crystallization and finally the solidified product is subcooled. Some products do not have a distinct solidification point, but rather a solidification temperature range²⁸. This process is commonly used in cosmetics and the pharmaceutical industry. Using this method the drugs can be suspended in molten wax and subsequently spray congealed. This resultant material can then be adapted for a prolonged release dosage form¹⁹. Typical carriers are fatty acids or alcohols, waxes, stearates or polyethylene glycols.

PROCESS PARAMETERS IN SPRAY DRYING^{28, 29}

Spray drying is a process in which a number of processing parameters have an influence on the characteristics of the final product. Thus it becomes a pre requisite to control the process parameters in order to obtain the product with the desired characteristics. Table 2 gives a good overall idea about how the characteristics of the product change with change in the parameters.

TABLE 2

Influence of various parameters on the product characteristics

Sr. No.	Parameter	Influence
1.	A higher aspirator rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Offers more drying energy and increases the outlet gas temperature. ➤ Offers more drying energy and results a smaller amount of residual moisture in the product. ➤ Results a higher degree of separation in the cyclone.
	A higher drying gas humidity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Means less vapour uptake capability in the gas stream. Saturation occurs easily leading to a higher outlet temperature. ➤ Might increase the humidity of the final product. ➤ Might result in moist particles, which could adhere to the glassware thereby decreasing the yield.
	A higher inlet temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Increases the outlet temperature proportionally. ➤ Reduces the relative humidity in the drying gas and the powder gets dryer. ➤ Offers a dryer product, which is less sticky and increases the yield.
	A higher spray gas flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Decreases the outlet temperature due to additional cold gas to heat up. ➤ Produces smaller droplets from the nozzle and the corresponding solid particle size decreases.
	A higher feed rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Means more liquid to evaporate and decreases the outlet temperature. ➤ Increases the droplet size because more liquid has to be dispersed. ➤ Increases the moisture content in the gas and might result in humid or moist products.
	A higher solid concentration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Means less liquid to vaporize and increases the outlet temperature. ➤ Results in more solids in a drop and increases the particle size. ➤ Produces bigger particles, which are easier to separate and the yield increases. ➤ Decreases the partial pressure of solvent in the gas and the final product humidity decreases.

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